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Content

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Sr. No	Title and Name of The Author (S)	Page No
1	Education Of Differently Abled Children: Governmental Interventions And Attainments Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel And Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari	1
2	Problems Faced By Rural Women Entrepreneurs In Karaikal District Of Puducherry (ut) P. Madhan Mohan Gandhi	6
3	A Study On Relationship Between Pro - Social Behaviour And Anti Social Behaviour Of Higher Secondary Students A. Paul Albert And T. Thilagavathy	10
4	रामचरितमानस: पाश्चात्य विद्वानों की दृष्टि में आभा एस. खेडेकर	12
5	US Foreign Policy Towards Africa In A Post - Cold War Era Alka Mudgal	14
6	Globalization And Decentralisation In India Ananga Bhima Biswal	18
7	Comparitive Study Of Mental Toughness Between The Players Of Tae-kwon - Do And Cricket Arjun Singh Solanki And M. K. Singh	21
8	Spatio-temporal Analysis Of Resource Base In North Kanara Coastal Zone, India Ashok Kumar	24
9	Gandhi And Untouchables In Mulk Raj Anand's " Untouchable " Debabrata Karmakar	32
10	Growth Of Population In Parbhani District - A Geographical Analysis. Devkar Bhausahab sonaji	35
11	Effect Of Supplementation Of "murraya Koenigii" And " Ocimum Sanctum Leaves" In Niddm Subjects. Jyothi. A , Rajani. N And Bramhini. M	37
12	Regional Analysis Of Male-female Differentials In Literacy In Western Satpura Region, India L. P. Sandanshiv	40
13	Comparison Between Selected Physiological And Physical Fitness Variables Among Swimmers, Athletes And Sedentary People Mahendra Kumar Singh And Arvind Bahadur Singh	43
14	Experience Of Women Advocates In Legal Profession : An Analysis Meharunnisa H. Hullur	48
15	वर्तमान दौर में उर्दू मीडिया : विशेषणात्मक अध्ययन मुहम्मद फरियाद ए मु.अफसर अली राईनी	52

EDUCATION OF DIFFERENTLY ABLED CHILDREN: GOVERNMENTAL INTERVENTIONS AND ATTAINMENTS

Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel And Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari

Associate Professor in Education, DDE, MANUU, Gachibowli, Hyderabad
Research Assistant, CSSEIP, DDE, MANUU, Gachibowli, Hyderabad

Abstract: *A rose is still a rose even when it loses a petal. A tree may lose some leaves, but it is still useful. Likewise, a human being can still be useful despite the loss of a physical faculty. Helen Keller says that the most unfortunate person in society is one who has sight but no vision. In order to understand the abilities of person with disabilities, one needs to have a broad vision of humanistic values. An inclusive society needs the support of parents, teachers, professionals and other community members.*

The term differently abled children has replaced disabled children, because each individual is bestowed with some or the other potentialities. But, to understand the concept of disability the definition given by the American Heritage Dictionary of English Language can be examined, "a disadvantage or deficiency, especially a physical or mental impairment that interferes with or prevent normal achievement in a particular area or something that hinders or incapacitates". The present paper tries to find out the population of disabled people in India in different disability categories. A mention of disability services in India during pre independence era, post independence era, DPEP. It is well known fact that the schools have an important role to play for training of differently abled children and the onus is rested with the government to take up new initiatives. The schemes like SSA have played an important role for education of this group in the present times. The paper attempts to explore services improvement of integrated education taken up under SSA and attempts to give objectives, scope, and intervention etc. This will be of great help for policy makers and planner as they are working for universalisation of elementary education, which could not be attend without educating this group.

Keywords: Education, Interventions and Attainments, humanistic values, society.

INTRODUCTION

A rose is still a rose even when it loses a petal. A tree may lose some leaves, but it still remains useful. Likewise a human being can still be useful despite the loss of a physical faculty. Helen Keller says that the most unfortunate person in society is one who has sight but no vision. In order to understand the abilities of person with disabilities, one needs to have a broad vision of humanistic values. An inclusive society needs the support of parents, teachers, professionals and other community members.

First of all we will see what the disability is? According to the American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language, "disability" is defined as a "a disadvantage or deficiency, especially a physical or mental impairment that interferes with or prevent normal achievement in a particular area or something that hinders or incapacitates". Definition of "Disability" contained in the Rehabilitation Act & the American with Disabilities Act, "Any individual who has a physical or mental impairment which substantially limits one or more of such person's major life activities, has a record of such impairment or is regarded as having such impairment".

In other words you are limited in what you can do because of your disability.

Definition of "Disability" contained in the

individuals with Disabilities Education Act: "A Physical or mental impairment that 'adversely affects a child's educational performance".

In other words you can't learn because of your disability.

Definition of "Disability" contained in the social security Act: "Disability" means inability to engage in any substantial gainful activity

In other words you can't work because of your disability. According to the prominent Disability Studies scholar and activists, Carol Gill (1998), the experience of disability has historically viewed as a "tangible flaw located within an individual's physical or mental constitution".

The unnamed speakers of the world define "disability" as a "limitation", a weakness" a "barrier to be overcome. Many disabled people today propose that they choose a new name for themselves and their community rather than "disability" such as "physically challenged", or differently abled persons".

According to the person with disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act 1995 "Person with disability" is defined as a person suffering from not less than forty percent of any disability is divided into seven groups; blindness, low vision, leprosy-cured, hearing impairment, locomotors disability, mental

retardation and mental illness with the exception of blindness each of these has a specific definition in the Act.

The population of disabled people in India as given by World bank of India from 36th and 47th NSSO is given in table 1 and figure 1.

Table disability-specific data

Physical Disability	Visual Impairment	Hearing Impairment	Speech disability	Locomotors Disability	Overlapping
41.32%	10.32%	8.36%	5.06%	23.04%	11.54%

Figure showing disability-specific data

HISTORY OF DISABILITY SERVICES IN INDIA

Historically organised attempts to educate blind children were made in India, when Christian Missionaries established schools. The first school for blind children was established by an English missionary known as Annie sharp in Amritsar in 1887.

MODELS FOR EDUCATION OF THE DISABLED

Services for the disabled in India are more than a century old. Four significant models are in vogue here

1. Residential school for the Disabled, Mostly Urban with special curriculum including vocational training. India has thousands such schools serving lakhs of children.
2. Integrated Education – Resource Room Model: One specialist resource teacher catering to 8-10 disabled children studying with and evaluated on par with normal children plus curricular skills are taught. This is the most prominent model in India now.
3. Integrated Education – Itinerant Model: Specialist itinerant teacher with resource kit visits a cluster of schools 2-3 times a week to assist the disabled. This is not a very popular mode.
4. Inclusive Education: All children with disabilities irrespective of severity enrolled in general schools. All teachers are oriented to their needs and this is currently preferred under EFA also because cost considerations favour inclusion.

Disability prevention refers to various medical measures taken to avert the causes of disability. Prevention is crucial in reducing the incidence of disability. In olden days the stigma associated with negative labels of the past the old language which labelled disabled people on their

imperfection was abandoned and replaced by the new language where by children with disabilities were described in more broader, more general terms such as 'children with special educational needs'.

Laws on Education of Disabled

The National Policy on Education 1986 advocates Integrated Education in general school for the locomotors impaired and mildly disabled children and special education for the severely handicapped children.

The Indian Government has laws and schemes to promote the education of disabled children at various levels (Central, State and local bodies). Free education is to be provided to all the disabled children under the age of 18. The Person with Disabilities Act 1995 also promotes the integration of disabled children into normal schools.

As per the act, Government should formulate schemes to provide part-time classes, non-formal education and education through open schools and universities for children with special needs. The Act envisages a comprehensive scheme with transport facilities, free books, uniform and other materials, schools without architectural barriers that provide a restructured curriculum a modified examination system as well as scholarship for the benefit of these children.

District Primary Education Programme (DPEP)

The DPEP has had a powerful impact integrating disabled children. The advantage of this scheme is that it took care of all areas from identification, assessment, enrolment and provision of appliances to total integration of disabled children in schools with resource support, teacher training and parental counselling.

Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment

The Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment provided several schemes to assist these children. The most important among them being assistance to voluntary organisation for special schools for the handicapped, assistance to the disabled person for purchasing appliances.

Integrated Education of Disabled Children (IEDC)

The Integrated Education of Disabled Children (IEDC) scheme was launched in 1991 implemented in 15,000 schools in 26 states and Union territories covered 65,000 disabled children in general schools. The scheme included pre-school training, counselling for parents, allowances for books and stationary, uniform, transport, reader and escort, hostel facilities and other assisting devices. The scheme provided one special teacher for every eight disabled children, community involvement and a resource room in a cluster of 8 to 10 schools.

Inclusive education

The special school for children with special needs has been a prevalent mode of teaching the disabled. This system has major drawbacks. It is expensive it has only a limited reach it segregates children based on disability which is discriminatory and violated human right. The philosophy of 'integration', advocated education of children with mild

and moderate disabilities in general schools with others, providing adequate resource support. This led to the concept of Inclusive Education (IE). IE is suitable on education at social and moral grounds. It makes classrooms responsive for the needs of the learner. It stresses on child centred pedagogy using peer tutoring, co-operative learning and group learning.

Sound Policy Perspectives and Practices

Inclusive education revolve round three main factor-policies, practices and cultures. The Disabilities Act 1995 aiming at the inclusion of disabled persons in the mainstream and the rehabilitation Council of India (RCI) Act 1992 is another impressive concept in maintaining quality in special education.

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA)

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) is a Government of India's flagship programme for achievement of Univesalisation of Elementary Education (UEE) in a time bound manner, as mandated by 86th amendment to constitution of India making free and compulsory education to the children of 6-14 years of age group, a Fundamental right. The programme sought to open new schools in those habitations which do not have schooling facilities and strengthens existing school infrastructure through provision of additional classrooms, toilets, drinking water, maintenance grant and school improvement grants-existing schools within adequate teacher strength are provided with additional teachers while the capacity of existing teachers is being strengthened by extensive training grants for developing teaching-learning material and strenghteing of the academic support structure at a cluster, block and district level. SSA seeks to provide quality elementary education including life skills. SSA has a special focus on girl's education and children with special needs.

Objectives of SSA

The objectives of SSA were as under,
Education shall become people's movement.
All children of age group 6-14 shall be in school by 2003.
All children complete five years of primary schooling by 2007.
All children complete eight years of elementary schooling by 2010.
All children would attain Minimum Levels of Learning with life related skills.
Bridge all gender and social category gaps at primary stage by 2007 and at elementary education level by 2010.
Universal retention by 2010.

Scope

The main aim of SSA was Universalisation of Elementary Education. Therefore, the scope was primary education up to 8th standard. The SSA is giving full stress on qualitative and quantitative improvement of primary education.

Intervention of SSA

The interventions given by SSA for following aspects,

1. Teacher
2. School
3. Upper Primary School
4. Class Room
5. Free Text Books
6. Civil work
7. Maintenance and repair of school building
8. School Grant
9. Teacher Grant
10. Teacher Training
11. Training of Community Leaders
12. Management cost
13. BRC/CRC
14. Preparatory activities

Special Interventions

1. Innovative activity for girls' education
2. Out of school children
3. Provision for disabled children

Inclusive Education in SSA

The key objective of SSA is Universalisation of Elementary Education (UEE). Three important aspects of UEE are access, enrolment and retention of all children in 6-14 years of age. This goal of UEE has further been facilitated by the constitutional (86th amendment). This amendment has given a new thrust to the education of children with special needs (CwSN) as without their inclusion, objective of UEE cannot be achieved. In fact inclusion of one of the groups which is extremely crucial for UEE is perhaps that of the component of SSA.

Provision for CwSN under SSA

The SSA provides a fixed amount per child per year as per specific proposal for the inclusion of disabled children. The interventions under SSA for inclusive education are identification - functional and formal assessment, appropriate educational placement, preparation of individualised education plan, provision of aids and appliances, teacher training, resource support, removal of architectural barriers, research monitoring and evaluation and a special focus on girls with special needs.

SSA's Policy on Inclusion

According to SSA a meaningful and quality education is to be provided to every child with special needs. Hence, SSA has adopted a zero rejection policy. This means that no child having special needs should be deprived of the right to education and taught in an environment, which is best suited to his/her learning needs. These include special schools, EGS, AIE or even home-based education.

The major thrust of SSA is on inclusion on mainstreaming of CwSN into fabric of formal elementary schooling. Most children with special needs can be enrolled or retained in regular school if adequate resource support is provided to them, where as there are others who might have to be provided some kind of pre-integration programmes, before they can be mainstreamed in a classroom. There might be still some CwSN with sever profound disabilities who would require an educational programme and intensive

specialised support completely beyond the purview and scope of a formal school in the current situation.

Thus, SSA adopted a more expansive and a broad-based understanding of concept of inclusion where in a multi-option mode of educating CwSN is being implemented.

Efforts so far made by SSA for Inclusive Education

In each programmes the implementation of this multi option mode of inclusive education has been done. Different states made different approaches to enrol the CwSN in schools under inclusive education of SSA. Rajasthan conducted bridge courses for CwSN through NGOs; UP conducted them through resource teachers especially recruited by the District SSA societies for this purpose. Andhra Pradesh adopted a mixed model; with some districts conducted these courses through NGOs and other through the District SSA societies. Besides this AIE model, 11 states covered are also covering CwSN through the EGS.

In 21 states another practice was adopted for sever-profound disabilities that home-based education either to prepare CwSN for school or to make them learn the basic living skills. States like Himachal Pradesh and Uttarakhand used NGO for this purpose where as states like Haryana and Kerala appointed resources teachers who visited the home of CwSN to provide them basic living skills.

Still other states like Tamil Nadu were using special schools as resource centres to provide short-time or part-time help to individual children with special needs. Through home-based education, SSA has been able to cover lakhs of CwSN.

Haryana had opened model of inclusive schools in every block and equipped them with all possible facilities (like transport, equipped for physio-therapy, occupational therapy, resource teachers etc.) mainly to provide all kinds of support services, including remedial teaching to CwSN. Many states have appointed resource teachers and some other states involved NGOs in the IE programme.

Education of CwSN in the context of special interventions of SSA in Andhra Pradesh

Andhra Pradesh, Rajiv Vidya Mission has designed interventions in conformity to the provisions of RTE Act to implement the constitutional imperatives to admit all out of school children in to age appropriate classes and support them till they complete elementary education. In case of children with special needs, the AP Mission has adapted different approaches and workable strategies to realise these mandates.

For, total 2,62,716 children who have been identified with special needs in the State 2,34,550 are enrolled in schools. Relevant education is being provided to 9,696 children with sever and profound disabilities at their homes through 1,485 special educators. 9,155 children were enrolled in Special Training Centers under school readiness programmes. Escort Allowance is being provided to those who require escort support to attend the schools. AP mission is taking initiation to support the children for minor corrective surgeries which could help the child to overcome his/her physical challenges in attending the school. By 2013

44,656 ramps were constructed in schools to enable the child to access the school conveniently. To meet the instant demand that comes from the children for supply of appliances, AP RVM (SSA) has maintained buffer stocks of assistive devices for the first time in the country. In the year 2012-13 assistive devices were provided to all the 11,604 children requiring appliances. Nearly, 16,900 children with neuro-muscular disorders are getting Physiotherapy in their mandal points. AP state, for the first time has reduced the age limit from 6 years to 4 years to provide early child interventions. 382 Inclusive Education Resource Centres were started to provide required therapeutic service to the children. Nearly, 7000 CwSN friendly toilet were sanctioned to the districts for construction in schools where the need is imminent.

Ongoing programme/activities

Identification of CwSN for assessment

Education at home

Buffer Stock – A solution for instant demands for appliances

Physiotherapy Services at MRC

Minor Surgical Corrections

Escort Allowance – A boon to many CwSN

Centres for early intervention support

Age-limit reduced to 4 years for CwSN

Inclusive KGBVs for CwSN

Revised Braille Text Books supplied

D.Ed. Course made inclusive in AP

Special training through GO-NGO partnership

Forthcoming programme/activities

Organising training programme to the Doctors of all Primary Health Centre Doctors in AP

Eye screening of all school age children in the state to provide spectacles

Organising Life Line Express (Hospital on Wheels) camp at districts like Anantapur for minor corrective strategies

Right to Education Act (2010) and Education of differently abled (CwSN)

The right to education act has got the approval of the President of India in 2009 and was enacted from 1st of April, 2010. This is called 'the right of children to free and compulsory education act, 2009'. The implementation of RTE act has increased responsibility of government manifold. The role of teachers, parents, administrators, government will have to designed as per the requirements of act, so that education can be provided to all the children irrespective of their backgrounds. This is why all children are to be educated including CwSN by accommodating their needs as educators.

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Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel
Associate Professor in Education, DDE,
MANUU, Gachibowli, Hyderabad

Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari
Research Assistant, CSSEIP, DDE,
MANUU, Gachibowli, Hyderabad